

Detection by Uv Spectra, of Compound Formation between Ethanol and certain Aryl Methyl Sulphoxides

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The uv spectra of a number of aryl methyl sulphoxides are recorded in both cyclohexane and ethanol. The data indicate compound formation between ethanol and sulphoxides in solution. Sulphoxides having substituents in both the *ortho*-positions, however, do not form such compound.

The possibility of aryl methyl sulphoxides interacting with alcohols in solution with compound formation as in 1 was noted by us earlier¹. Later, while conducting phase rule studies with binary mixtures of sulphoxides and phenols, we observed² compound formation between methyl *p*-nitrophenyl sulphoxide and *p*-nitrophenol. Compound 2 was

actually prepared in the solid state². In view of the rarity of sulphur exhibiting qudrivalency in organic compounds, we thought it of interest to study the problem further. The study involved examining the uv spectra of a number of sulphoxides in cyclohexane and ethanol. For comparison the uv spectra of some sulphides and sulphones in the same solvents were also taken.

Results and Discussion

The spectral data of sulphoxides (Table 1) reveal

that methyl phenyl sulphoxide, methyl *p*-tolyl sulphoxide, methyl *p*-nitrophenyl sulphoxide and methyl 4-methoxyphenyl sulphoxide show a notable solvent effect, the λ_{\max} in cyclohexane being very much higher than that in ethanol. This indicates that electronic excitation of the above sulphoxides is more difficult in ethanol than in cyclohexane. A possible explanation for this is that ethanol interacts with the sulphoxides forming compounds like 1. There can, however, be an argument that compound formation need not be invoked because stabilisation of the ground state by solvation itself can explain the observed phenomenon. The subsequent discussion will show the inadequacy and incorrectness of such a view.

From the data given in Table 2 it is obvious that the spectral characteristics of sulphoxides, which exhibit the solvent effect, are practically the same in 95% ethanol and absolute ethanol. Hence, it is ethanol and not water that interacts with sulphoxides.

Mono-*ortho*-substituted aryl methyl sulphoxides (Sl. nos. 3 and 6 of Table 1) also show the above-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF ARYL METHYL SULPHOXIDES

Sl. no.	Aryl	B.p. (mm Hg)/ M.p. °C	Lit. B.p.(mm Hg) M.p. °C	Cyclohexane λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) nm	Ethanol λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) nm
1.	Phenyl	118–20(5)	144(15) ^b	253 (4 000)	237 (4 100)
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	138–40(12)	118–19(2.5) ^c	249 (3 300)	237 ^f (4 900)
3.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl ^{a, b}	159–61(20)	—	251 (3 300)	236 (3 400)
4.	2,6-Dimethylphenyl ^{a, d}	140–41(3.5)	—	272 (2 200)	275 (1 900)
				261 (2 000)	259 (2 050)
5.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	147–48	146–47 ^c	296 (5 600)	286 (6 900)
6.	2-Methyl-4-nitrophenyl ^{a, d}	122–23	—	299 (6 000)	289 (6 200)
				248 (8 100)	252 (6 100)
7.	2,6-Dimethyl-4-nitrophenyl	165–66	165–66 ^e	311 (4 700)	310 (4 800)
8.	2,6-Dibromo-4 nitrophenyl	128–29	128–29 ^e	257 (8 600)	260 (7 900)
				319 (2 800)	317 (2 700)
				261 (6 400)	263 (6 400)
9.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	134–35(0.75)	45–46 ^c	254 (11 800)	243 (12 300)
10.	4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl ^{a, d}	136–37 (2)	—	256 (9 600)	245 (9 800)
11.	4-Methoxy-2,6-dimethylphenyl ^{a, d}	164–66 (1.2)	—	241 (6 800)	240 (7 000)

^aSamples used were those prepared by the authors for another study. ^bRef. 3. ^cRef. 4. ^dRef. 5. ^eRef. 6. ^fShoulder.

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TABLE 2—UV SPECTRA OF SULPHOXIDES IN 95% ETHANOL AND ABSOLUTE ETHANOL

Sulphoxide	Ethanol λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) nm	Absolute ethanol λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) nm
Methyl phenyl	237 (4 100)	237 (4 100)
Methyl <i>p</i> -tolyl	249 (3 300)	249 (3 350)
Methyl <i>o</i> -tolyl	236 (3 400)	237 (3 450)
Methyl <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	243 (12 300)	243 (12 400)

mentioned solvent effect. But di-*ortho*-substituted sulphoxides (Sl. nos. 4, 7, 8 and 11) behave differently. Their spectral characteristics in both cyclohexane and ethanol are almost the same. This affords clue to the view that sulphoxides with no steric hindrance only react with ethanol to form compounds of the type 1. When substituents are present in both positions *ortho* to the sulphinyl group, compound formation is not possible due to steric hindrance. This should be the reason for di-*ortho*-substituted sulphoxides, having similar spectral characteristics in cyclohexane and ethanol.

Compounds resulting by the interaction of sulphoxides and ethanol are not insoluble but exist only in solution. The only known identifiable solid compound is 2. It may be mentioned here that no phenol other than *p*-nitrophenol has been found to react with methyl *p*-nitrophenyl sulphoxide to yield such a solid product.

In the light of the solvent effect shown by unhindered sulphoxides, it was thought of interest to examine the spectral behaviour of sulphides and sulphones also in the same two solvents. The recorded spectral data are given in Table 3. The solvent effect is negligible for sulphides and sulphones. Ethanol cannot react with them in the way it does with unhindered sulphoxides. Thus the behaviour of sulphinyl group is unique and interesting.

The fact that sulphones have the same spectral characteristics in both cyclohexane and ethanol, rules out the possibility that H-bond formation in ethanol is the cause of sulphoxides having different spectral characteristics in ethanol and cyclohexane. If H-bond formation is responsible for the observed

difference, then a similar difference should be observable in the case of sulphones also.

TABLE 3—UV SPECTRA OF SULPHIDES AND SULPHONES IN CYCLOHEXANE AND ETHANOL

Compd.	Cyclohexane	Ethanol
	λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) nm	λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max}) nm
	Sulphide	
Methyl phenyl	235 (9 500)	254 (9 600)
Methyl <i>p</i> -tolyl	257 (9 600)	256 (9 800)
Methyl <i>o</i> -tolyl	252 (8 400)	251 (8 600)
Methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl	220 (9 300)	219 (9 400)
	Sulphone	
Methyl phenyl	217 (7 000)	217 (6 800)
Methyl <i>p</i> -tolyl	225 (12 000)	225 (11 800)
Methyl <i>o</i> -tolyl	219 (7 300)	219 (7 200)
Methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl	219 (7 400)	219 (7 400)

Experimental

The sulphoxides (Table 1) were prepared as described in the literature^{3,4}. The sulphides⁵ and sulphones⁶ were prepared as described in earlier papers.

The uv spectra were recorded in ethanol and cyclohexane with a Hilger and Watts UVISPEK spectrophotometer. Unless otherwise specified, the alcohol used was 95% ethanol. The cyclohexane (B.D.H.) used was of spectrograde quality.

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